

DCC2GO Starter-Kit

General resources

General documentation resources

ID	Ressource	Type	Description	Provider	Link
1	DCC2GO Training Compendium	training	The DCC training compendium includes an overview on the current state-of-the-art of DCC development and usage. It covers a range of information from the basic properties and advantages of DCCs for National Metrology Institutes, Designated Institutes and their stakeholders, to full technical specifications for metrology practitioners and technical support (e.g., IT information), to overview documents for senior management and other stakeholder organisations in the metrology community.	DCC2GO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199281
2	DCC2GO Guideline Start working with DCCs	guideline	This guideline addresses such issues as how to create a DCC, what IT infrastructure is needed and how to deal with the IT tools for handling the DCC.	DCC2GO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199700
3	DCC2GO Guideline DCC protection and security	guideline	This guideline focuses on aspects of protection and secure submission of DCCs. It comprises different types of mechanisms for securing the content of DCCs such as digital signatures.	DCC2GO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199700
4	DCC2GO Example temperature DCC	example	This suit of slides, data, and software provides an easy-to-follow step-by-step guideline allowing users to create and explore their first XML DCC and PDF/A-3 DCC example based on temperature calibration data. It demonstrates a quick (and dirty) approach based open access software tools.	DCC2GO	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199718
5	Proceedings 3rd International DCC conference	proceedings	Collection of presentations given at the 3rd International DCC conference 28. February - 2 March 2023, Braunschweig, Germany	PTB	https://doi.org/10.7795/810.20230331
6	Proceedings 2nd International DCC conference	proceedings	Collection of presentations given at the 3rd International DCC conference 28. February - 2 March 2023, Braunschweig, Germany	PTB	https://doi.org/10.7795/820.20220411

Committees dealing with DCCs

	EURAMET TC-IM 1448	working group	The goal of this group is to foster the development of harmonised digital calibration certificates (DCC) at national metrology institutes and calibration laboratories within EURAMET.	EURAMET	web page
	SIM MWG.14 TF DCC	working group	The goal of this task force is to exchange information on DCCs within SIM's NMIs.	SIM	https://www.cenam.mx/m4dt-sim/TaskForce/Category/DCC

	DKD (calibration service Germany)	committee	The working groups of the german calibration service started in 2022 the harmonization of DCC creation. The develop guidelines for users in industry and accredited laboratories how to write DCCs in a common and machine-interoperable way.	DKD	https://www.ptb.de/cms/en/metrological-services/dkd.html
--	-----------------------------------	-----------	---	-----	---

Surveys on DCCs

7	Report on the 2022 survey of CC participants	report	The CIPM initiated a survey on the current and planned activities of National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) on digitalization. A questionnaire was designed and circulated to recent delegates of all CIPM Consultative Committees (CCs). Among the different DT topics, digital calibration certificates were the most mentioned topic of interest to NMIs.	BIPM	web page
8	Digital transformation of calibration data management	master thesis	In this research, the industrial implementation of digital calibration certificates was investigated. The primary objectives of the research were to identify the early adopters of the DCC and the main drivers and blockers of the implementation.	Aalto	https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi/handle/123456789/110583

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. DOI 110.5281/zenodo.8199700

DCC2GO Starter-Kit

Resources for XML DCC

Official material and documentation

ID	Resource	Type	Description	Provider	Link
1	Official web page	web page	Access to all resources defining the generic DCC XML schema, documentation, training, events, etc.	PTB	https://ptb.de/dcc
	DCC tutorial	videos	A set of recorded presentations providing an overview to the XML DCC and its application. The language is English.	PTB	https://www.ptb.de/dcc/videos_tutorial
	DCC User Forum	consulting hours	Weekly online meeting for users allowing to ask questions to DCC experts. It is a kind of level 1 support help desk.	PTB	User-Forum
	DCC XML Schema	implementation	An XML Schema file that defines the common data structure of the DCC. It is a kind of pattern defining the buildingblocks one can use to write DCC files.	PTB	https://www.ptb.de/dcc/dcc.xsd
	DCC Git Repository	repository	An online software repository where the development of the DCC XML Schema is managed.	PTB	https://gitlab.com/ptb/dcc
	DCC Wiki	Wiki	The documentation of the DCC XML Schema where its elements (buildingblocks) are described. The wiki is provided as a web page.	PTB	https://dccwiki.ptb.de/en/publications
	D-SI XML Schema	implementation	D-SI is the universal datamodel for the representation of quantity values. It is used by the DCC to implement measured quantities, constants and all parameters referring to physical quantity values in a DCC.	SmartCom/PTB	https://www.ptb.de/si/SI_Format.xsd
	D-SI Git Repository	repository	An online software repository where the development of the D-SI XML Schema is managed. This repository includes a wide range of application examples and the official documentation of the D-SI XML implementation.	SmartCom/PTB	https://gitlab1.ptb.de/d-ptb/d-si/xsd-d-si
	D-SI brochure	guideline	A PDF document with the high-level documentation of the D-SI metadata model on which the D-SI XML schema is based.	SmartCom/PTB	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3816686

Documentation, training and instruction from various providers

ID	Resource	Type	Description	Provider	Link
	DCC, Step by step, Guide to learning essential concepts	guideline	A set of slides explaining the basic about DCCs. The material is part of the information exchange on DCCs implemented by SIM.	SIM	PDF file
	eAttestation seal by DAkkS	project	Germany's national accreditation body DAkkS runs a project to implement a digital verification of DCCs from accredited laboratories (eAttestation). This reference provides information on the project from DAkkS.	DAkkS	web page
	DKD expert report on DCCs for weights	guideline	Instructions on how to use the DCC schema to create a digital calibration certificate for weights : Expert Report DKD-E 7-2	DKD	https://doi.org/10.7795/550.20220419B

	Document specifying rules for the secure use of DCC covering legal aspects of metrology	report	EMPIR 17IND02 SmartCom: Report on legal aspects and cryptographic security of DCCs.	SmartCom	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3664211
--	---	--------	---	----------	---

Tools for creating and using the XML DCC

ID	Resource	Type	Description	Provider	Link
	Gemimeg Tool	web tool	This tool is a web-based editor for creating and reading DCCs. Currently it is a demonstrator software allowing users to enter data to a dcc without requiring to work with XML. Data is entered into web forms and automatically converted to the XML. Furthermore, human-readable representation of the data and PDF/A-3 output can also be created.	PTB/ Gemimeg	https://www.gemimeg.ptb.de/gemimeg-tool/#/
	CSV2DCC	software	The purpose of the CSV2DCC application is to embed metrology data held within a CSV (actually a semicolon separated) file into a Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) XML file. The application runs with Java Runtime Environment.	PTB	https://github.com/PTB-M4D/CSV2DCC
	Excel DCC Tool	software	This tool demonstrates how to use an Excel sheet with VBA elements as user interface for creating an XML DCC.	PTB	https://doi.org/10.1016/i.measen.2021.100175
?	Anu VTT DCC Excel / Paper	software		VTT (/NPL)	
	PyDCC	software	PyDCC is a library for reading and evaluating digital calibration certificates (DCCs) according to the official DCC version 3.0.0. It is made for Python.	Gemimeg	https://pypi.org/project/pydcc/
	anyDCC	software	One of the first commercial softwares for creating DCCs.	Stotz Software	https://www.digitaler-kalibrierschein.de/
	Tiny Demonstrator: Temperature Calibration with Arduino Sensor Kit	software	Educational example for automated calibration measurement and data processing using an Excel macro reading temperature data from an IoT device. The data is processed into D-SI XML data for DCCs.	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6459280

Publications on recent developments and application examples

ID	Resource	Type	Description	Provider	Link
	A HUMAN READABLE FORM OF THE DCC	proceedings	This paper shows how to generate the human readable form of the DCC by using the eXtensible Stylesheet Language (XSLT).	IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.035
	INPUT MANAGEMENT FOR THE DCC	proceedings	This publication breaks down the necessary information to generate a DCC. It distinguishes between general and specific specifications and shows which information in addition to the DCC schema is necessary to generate a machine interpretable DCC.	IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.034
	RECENT ADVANCES OF THE LONG-TERM AVAILABLE DCC SCHEMA VERSION 3	proceedings	This publication provides an overview of the recent advances of the XML schema for digital calibration certificates at the time of end of 2022.	IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.033

DIGITAL SCHEMAX AND THE FUTURE OF THE DIGITAL CALIBRATION CERTIFICATE	proceedings	Th paper outlines some new developments of the DCC and describes future planned developments. It present the new Digital SchemaX (DX), which has been developed for DCC version 4. Second, an Envelope Digital Certificate (EDC) has been prepared to collect different calibration items that belong together. Third, a planned new schema for Digital Reference Materials (DRM) is briefly introduced. Fourth, a planned schema for Digital Test Certificates (DTC), which are based on test reports is described.	IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.028
The Storage within Digital Calibration Certificates of Uncertainty Information Obtained Using a Monte Carlo Method	paper	This paper considers the use of a Monte Carlo method for uncertainty evaluation in calibration, using two examples to demonstrate how so-called 'digital calibration certificates' can allow the complete set of results of a Monte Carlo calculation to be reported.	MDPI	https://doi.org/10.3390/metrology2010003
Towards a new generation of digital calibration certificate: Analysis and survey	paper	The paper presents a thorough analysis of the DCC and the calibration process. Besides that, this work provides an overview of the carried research on that point to help peer researchers to view the big picture and to avoid wasting their efforts in repeating same work on same ideas.	ELSEVIER	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2021.109611

A digital framework for metrological information		A digital-system structure is very important for developing Metrology for Digital Transformation (M4DT) at NMIs. A plan for the digital transformation in metrology at the National Institute of Metrology (NIM), China is proposed	ELSEVIER	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2021.100122
SMART INFRASTRUCTURE FOR DEVELOPING DIGITAL CALIBRATION CERTIFICATES AT SASO-NMCC	proceedings	This work presents the efforts at SASO-NMCC of Saudi Arabia towards modifying its work processes for replacing analog calibration certificates with the modern DCCs. A smart e-infrastructure for issuing DCCs is proposed.	IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.044
Preliminary E-infrastructure for Digital Calibration Certificate	paper	This work presents the efforts at SASO-NMCC of Saudi Arabia towards modifying its work processes for replacing analog calibration certificates with the modern DCCs. A smart e-infrastructure for issuing DCCs is proposed.	ELSEVIER	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2021.100332
A Distributed Calibration Certificate Infrastructure	paper	This work proposes a DLT-based Distributed Calibration Certificate Infrastructure to manage calibration certificates. The proposed solution makes calibration certificates accessible and enables metrological traceability.	IEEE Explore	https://doi.org/10.1109/BRAINS55737.2022.9909437
The Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) for an End-to-End Digital Quality Infrastructure for Industry 4.0	paper	This article depicts the role of the Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) for an end-to-end digital quality infrastructure and as the basis for developments that are designated by the keyword "Industry 4.0".	MDPI/ GEMIMEG	https://doi.org/10.3390/sci5010011
GEMIMEG-II — How metrology can go digital	paper	The GEMIMEG-II project is intended to pave the way for digitalization in metrology. The central element of this digitalization initiative is the digital calibration certificate (DCC). This paper reflects the project status of GEMIMEG-II in its final phase and shares some insights on the concepts developed and solutions implemented as the results will be demonstrated in five Realbeds.	IOP/ GEMIMEG	https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/ace468

Calibration 4.0 – Information system for usage of digital calibration certificates	proceedings	This study is to operationalize the emission, exchange and use of digital calibration certificates, through structured information and the specification of a system of information.	CIM	https://doi.org/10.1051/metrology/201901002
Automated calibration and DCC generation system with storage in private permissioned Blockchain network	paper	The paper presents the possibility of joining the automated calibration system and the creation of a Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) with the Blockchain technology for storing and validation.	ACTA IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/actaimeko.v12i1.1414
Tracking and viewing modifications in digital calibration certificates	paper	This work presents a prototype web application developed in the programming language Links for storing and displaying a DCC using a relational database. In particular, it leverages the temporal database features that Links provides to capture different versions of a certificate and inspect differences between versions.	ACTA IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/actaimeko.v12i1.1407
Kennet Riskas Master Thesis ,Digital Calibration Certificate as part of an Ecosystem	thesis	In this research, the possibilities of establishing a new DCC ecosystem were investigated as well as how the ecosystem should be realized. It was also investigated what the benefits and disadvantages are of either a closed or open DCC ecosystem.	Novia	Thesis

Metrological Challenges in Collaborative Sensing: Applicability of Digital Calibration Certificates	paper	IoT systems based on collaborative sensor networks are becoming increasingly common in various industries. The quality of the data provided by these sensors may be unknown. This problem can be solved by the ongoing digitalization of the metrology infrastructure. We propose a conceptual solution based on Digital Calibration Certificates (DCCs), Digital SI (D-SI), and cryptographic digital identifiers, for validation of data quality and trustworthiness.	MDPI	https://doi.org/10.3390/s20174730
Benefits of network effects and interoperability for the digital calibration certificate management	paper	Platform economy and anti-rival data sharing have been proven to be an efficient way of creating additional value within organisations and value chains. Scalability and centralised development of the tools and software needed for the communication and system integration reduce the total development costs within the ecosystem.	IEEE Explore	https://doi.org/10.1109/MetroInd4.0IoT51437.2021.9488562
Digital Calibration Certificate in an industrial application	paper	This study demonstrated a fully digitalized environment for the calibration data generation, transfer, and usage in a Proof of Concept (PoC) project. Various stages of the PoC and different information systems used by the partners Aalto University, VTT MIKES, Beamex, Vaisala and Orion are discussed.	ACTA IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/actaimeko.v12i1.1402
PROMISING BENEFITS OF AN SELF-UPDATING (U)DCC APPLICATION EXAMPLE: THE QUANTUM-BASED PASCAL	proceedings	The DCC enables an updatable and thus improvable uncertainty budget. A direct benefit of the updatable DCC (UDCC) for the device under test (DUT) and thus for the end users would be the transfer of improvements with respect to the uncertainties of the primary standards. An illustrative application example is the new realization of the Pascal via quantum-based methods, such as primary standards using Fabry-Perot (FP) refractometry.	PTB/IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.040

THE DIGITAL NIST: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF NIST'S CALIBRATION SERVICES	proceedings	This work focuses on the digital calibration reports. It describes the pilot project to generate a digital calibration report from calibration data, customer metadata, and other data and metadata as needed; to generate a human readable report from the digital calibration report; and to collect feedback from stakeholders.	NIST/IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.039
Secure Exchange of Digital Metrological Data in a Smart Overhead Crane	paper	The implementation of DCC technologies in industrial applications is demonstrated with a use case of data exchange in a smart overhead crane. The presented system was tested and validated in providing security against data tampering attacks.	MDPI	https://doi.org/10.3390/s22041548
Digitalization of Calibration Data Management in Pharmaceutical Industry Using a Multitenant Platform	paper	For digitalizing the calibration-related data exchange, a multitenant cloud platform-based method is presented.	MDPI	https://doi.org/10.3390/app12157531
Pressure Calibration of Quarter-Inch Working Standard Microphones by Comparison	paper	The Standards and Calibration Laboratory (SCL) in Hong Kong has developed a system for calibration of quarter-inch working standard (WS3) microphones which automates the measurement process and generates digital calibration certificates (DCCs) to meet the growing demand for microphone calibration services in Hong Kong.	NCSLI	https://doi.org/10.51843/measure.14.1.7
Example of Force Digital Calibration Certificate used in ComTraForce 18SIB08 project to demonstrate Digital Twin concept	example	Force Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) was developed in the frameworks of 18SIB08 ComTraForce project. It was used to demonstrate the way of data connection between the physical object (force transducer) and virtual object (Finite Element model) within the developed Digital Twin concept.	ComTraForce	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7870845

FROM DIGITAL DEVICE UNDER TEST TO DIGITAL CALIBRATION CERTIFICATE. CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS FOR THE CALIBRATION OF MEASURING INSTRUMENTS AND SENSORS IN THE DIGITAL FUTURE	proceedings	The authors have to deal with both challenges as manufacturers of calibration systems and as operators of an accredited calibration laboratory. This paper tries to show why both areas are closely linked and how SPEKTRA deals with it.	IMEKO	https://doi.org/10.21014/tc6-2022.020
Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) – What is it and why should you care?	whitepaper	Beamex blog provides insightful information for calibration professionals, technical engineers as well as potential and existing Beamex users.	Beamax	web page
Digital Calibration Certificates in IoT	whitepaper	Short outline of the value of DCCs for IoT applications.	Force technology	PDF file
Kern test service	brochure	Short listing of DCC benefits in context of industrial calibration.	Kern calibration	PDF file

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. 10.5281/zenodo.8199700

DCC2GO Starter-Kit

Resources for PDF/A-3 DCC

ID	Resource	Type	Description	Provider	Link
1	PDF/A-3 solution for digital calibration certificates	documentation	This work proposes an approach for digital calibration certificates (DCCs) based on a PDF/A-3 solution that could be a stepping-stone towards the digitalization of metrological services. It presents multiple applications of this approach by fulfilling discussed minimum requirements and satisfying needs from both customers and laboratories.	ELSEVIER	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2021.100282
	METAS eCertificate	software	METAS eCertificate is a LaTeX template for an electronic calibration certificate with embedded data files.	GitHub	https://github.com/wollmich/metas-ecertificate
	MiKTeX	software	MiKTeX is a modern TeX distribution for Windows, Linux and macOS.	MiKTeX	https://miktex.org/
	Hash tool	web service	Calculation of different Hash Type values for data and files	fileformat.info	https://www.fileformat.info/tool/md5sum.htm
	Hash tool	web service	Calculation of different Hash Type values for data and files	xorbin.com	https://xorbin.com/tools/sha256-hash-calculator
	XML to JSON converter	web service	Transforming XML structured data into JSON structured data	Freeformatter	https://www.freeformatter.com/xml-to-json-converter.html
	Update of the BIPM comparison BIPM.RI(II)-K1.Ce-139	report	A publication of a Key Comparison report where the results are attached as machine-readable XML and JSON files to the report PDF using the PDF/A-3 DCC concept.	IOP	https://doi.org/10.1088/0026-1394/59/1A/06019
	NMIJ news letter		Information on an initiative exploring the use of PDF/A-3 at NMIJ in 2022.	NMIJ	PDF file

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199700